

Trivalent transition metal complexes derived from thiocarbohydrazide and dimedone

Dharam Pal Singh* and Parveen

Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

E-mail : dpsinghchem@yahoo.co.in, rathiparveen28@gmail.com Fax : 91-1744-238050

Manuscript received online 30 April 2013, revised 24 May 2013, accepted 25 May 2013

Abstract : A series of complexes of the type $[M(\text{TML})\text{X}]_2$; where TML is a tetradentate macrocyclic ligand, $M = \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ and Fe^{III} , $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, CH_3COO^- or NO_3^- , have been synthesized by template condensation reaction of dimedone and thiocarbohydrazide in the presence of trivalent metal salts in a methanolic medium. The complexes have been characterized with the help of elemental analyses, conductance measurements, magnetic measurements, electronic, infrared, far infrared and Mass spectral studies. On the basis of all these studies, a five coordinated square pyramidal geometry has been proposed for all these complexes. These metal complexes have also been tested for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activities against some bacterial strains and some fungal strains.

Keywords : Thiocarbohydrazide, tetradentate ligand, template, IR, antimicrobial.

Introduction

The family of complexes with aza-macrocyclic ligand has remained a focus of scientific attention for many decades¹. Macrocyclic compounds and their derivatives are interesting ligand system because they are good hosts for metal anions, neutral molecules and organic cation guests². The synthetic, kinetic and structural aspects of poly-aza macrocyclic complexes have received considerable attention and a variety of such systems have been synthesized³⁻⁶. Synthetic macrocyclic complexes mimic some naturally occurring macrocycles because of their resemblance to many natural macrocycles, such as metalloproteins, porphyrins and cobalamine^{7,8}. The poly-aza macrocycles particularly octa-aza macrocycles have been widely studied. Now a day's various strategies are available to design and development of molecular systems of the biological and medical importance⁹. Transition metal macrocyclic complexes have received great attention due to their biological activities, including antiviral, anticarcinogenic⁸, antifertile¹⁰, antibacterial and antifungal¹¹.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals and solvents used in this study were

of AnalaR grade. Dimedone were procured from Acros, New Jersey, USA. The metal salts were purchased from S.D.-fine, Mumbai, India, Merck, Ranbaxy, India and were used as received.

Isolation of complex :

Several attempts to isolate the free macrocyclic ligand were unsuccessful. Hence, all the complexes were synthesized by template method i.e. by condensation of thiocarbohydrazide and dimedone in the presence of the respective trivalent metal salt. To a hot stirring methanolic solution ($\sim 50 \text{ cm}^3$) of thiocarbohydrazide (10 mmol) was added trivalent chromium or iron salt (5.0 mmol) dissolved in the minimum quantity of methanol ($\sim 20 \text{ cm}^3$). The resulting solution was refluxed for 0.5 h. Subsequently, dimedone (10 mmol) was added to the refluxing mixture and refluxing was continued for 8–10 h. The mixture was cooled to room temperature whereby dark coloured precipitates formed which were filtered, washed with methanol, acetone and diethyl ether and dried in vacuum. The purity of complexes was checked by TLC. The synthesis of complexes may be shown by the Scheme 1.

Complex **1** : $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$: yield 49%, dark grey, Calcd. : M, 8.98; C, 37.34; H, 4.84; N,

Scheme 1. Scheme for synthesis of complexes derived from thiocarbohydrazide and dimedone with trivalent chromium and iron metal salts.

19.36. Found : M, 8.90; C, 37.24; H, 4.76, N, 18.99;
 $\Lambda_M = 140$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.35$ B.M.

Complex 2 : $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$: yield 50%, brown, Calcd. M, 7.90; C, 32.82; H, 4.25; N, 23.41. Found : M, 7.59; C, 32.67; H, 4.12; N, 23.37; $\Lambda_M = 160$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.61$ B.M.

Complex 3 : $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{OAc}](\text{OAc})_2$: yield 45%, light brown, Calcd. M, 8.01; C, 44.38; H, 5.70; N, 17.26. Found : M, 7.88; C, 44.25; H, 5.56; N, 17.13; $\Lambda_M = 170$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.70$ B.M.

Complex 4 : $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$: yield 45%, grey, Calcd. M, 9.59; C, 37.09; H, 4.81; N, 19.23. Found : M, 9.48; C, 37.10; H, 4.77; N, 19.09; $\Lambda_M = 155$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.78$ B.M.

Complex 5 : $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$: yield 47%, brown, Calcd. M, 8.44; C, 32.63; H, 4.23; N, 23.28. Found : M, 7.99; C, 32.46; H, 4.19; N, 23.10; $\Lambda_M = 170$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.92$ B.M.

Complex 6 : $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{OAc}](\text{OAc})_2$: yield 45%, reddish brown, Calcd. M, 8.55; C, 44.11; H, 5.67; N, 17.16. Found : M, 8.41; C, 44.02; H, 5.17; N, 17.16; $\Lambda_M = 142$, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.85$ B.M.

Analytical and physical measurements :

The microanalysis for C, H and N were carried out at IIT, Bombay using a Thermofinnigan chns-o analyser. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at SAIF, IIT Roorkee, on a vibrating sample magnetometer (Model PAR 155). The metal contents in the complexes were determined by literature methods¹². The IR spectra were recorded on a FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer RX-1) in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded at room temperature on a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer in the range 200–1100 nm. The conductivity was measured on a digital conductivity meter (HPG system, G-3001). The melting points were determined in capillaries using electric melting point apparatus.

Biological assay :

Test microorganisms :

Total six microbial strains were selected on the basis of their clinical importance in causing diseases in humans. Two Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 121); two Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* MTCC 1652 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* MTCC 741) and two yeast (*Can-*

didia albicans MTCC 3017 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* MTCC 170) were screened for evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activity of the complexes. All the microbial cultures were procured from Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC), IMTECH, Chandigarh. The bacteria were subcultured on Nutrient agar whereas yeast on Malt yeast agar. The antimicrobial activities and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) were determined as per literature method¹³.

Results and discussion

Chemistry :

The analytical data of the metal complexes shows that the formula of macrocyclic complexes may be represented as : $[M(C_{18}H_{28}N_8S_2)X]X_2$; where $M = Cr^{III}$ and Fe^{III} and $X = Cl^-$, NO_3^- and CH_3COO^- . The complexes were soluble in DMSO and DMF. They decompose above 300 °C without melting. The test for anions was positive before and after decomposing the complexes, indicating their presence inside as well as outside the coordination sphere. The monomeric nature of these complexes was confirmed by the molecular weight measurements. Conductivity measured in DMSO indicated them to be 1 : 2 electrolyte ($140-180 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$)¹⁴. Several attempts to obtain a single crystal, suitable for X-ray crystallography were unsuccessful. However the analytical, spectroscopic and magnetic data enable us to predict the structure of the complexes.

IR spectra :

The presence of a single medium band present in the range $3243-3310 cm^{-1}$ may be assigned to (N-H) stretch¹⁵ of thiocarbohydrazide. A pair of bands present in the spectrum of thiocarbohydrazide at 3260 and $3387 cm^{-1}$ corresponding to $\nu(NH_2)$, were absent in the infrared spectra of all the complexes. Furthermore, no strong absorption band was observed near $1715 cm^{-1}$, indicating the absence of the C=O group of the dimedone. The disappearance of these bands and appearance of a new strong band near $1590-1630 cm^{-1}$ points towards the condensation of the carbonyl group of dimedone and the amino group of thiocarbohydrazide and the formation of macrocyclic Schiff's base¹⁶, as these bands may be assigned to $\nu(C=N)$ stretching vibrations^{17,18}. The lower value of $\nu(C=N)$ may be explained based on a drift of the lone pair density of the azomethine nitrogen towards the metal

atom^{17,18} indicating that coordination occurred through the nitrogen of the C=N groups. The medium intensity bands present in the region $2830-2950 cm^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu(C-H)$ stretching vibrations of the methyl groups of the dimedone moiety. The presence of the absorption bands at $1408-1440$, $1290-1320$ and $1010-1030 cm^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of all the nitrate complexes suggest that both nitrate groups are coordinated to the central metal ion in a unidentate fashion¹. The IR spectra of all the acetate complexes show an absorption band in the region $1650-1670 cm^{-1}$ i.e. assigned to the $\nu(COO^-)$ as asymmetric stretching vibrations of the acetate ion and another in the region $1258-1280 cm^{-1}$ that can be assigned to the $\nu(COO^-)$ symmetric stretching vibrations of the acetate ion. The difference between ν_{as} and ν_s , which was around $390-370 cm^{-1}$ i.e. greater than $144 cm^{-1}$, indicates the unidentate coordination of the acetate group with the central metal ion¹⁹. The sulphur atom was not coordinated to central metal ion, as indicated by the absence of characteristic band. The C-N stretch occurs in the range $1350-1000 cm^{-1}$.

The far infrared spectra show bands in the region $430-470 cm^{-1}$ corresponding to $\nu(M-N)$ vibrations²⁰. The presence of bands in all complexes in the region $430-470 cm^{-1}$, originating from (M-N) azomethine vibrational modes, identify coordination of the azomethine nitrogen²¹. The bands present in the range $300-320 cm^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu(M-Cl)$ vibrations. The bands present in the region $220-250 cm^{-1}$ in all nitrate complexes are related to $\nu(M-O)$ stretching vibrations^{21,22}.

Magnetic measurements and electronic spectra :

Chromium complexes :

The magnetic moments of the chromium(III) complexes at room temperature were found in the range $4.35-4.70$ B.M., which are close to the predicted values for three unpaired electrons in the metal ion^{23,24}. The electronic spectra of the chromium complexes show bands at $9000-9290$ ($\epsilon = 6.59 \times 10^4 L mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$), $13230-13500$ ($\epsilon = 3.43 \times 10^4 L mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$), $16880-17310$ ($\epsilon = 5.04 \times 10^4 L mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$), $25280-25520$ ($\epsilon = 6.11 \times 10^4 L mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$) and $35715 cm^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 6.18 \times 10^4 L mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$). These spectral bands are consistent with that of a five coordinated square pyramidal geometry of chromium complexes, the structure of which were confirmed with

the help of X-ray measurements²⁵. Thus assuming C_{4v} symmetry for these complexes^{26,27} the various bands may be assigned as : ${}^4B_1 \rightarrow {}^4E^a$, ${}^4B_1 \rightarrow {}^4B_2$, ${}^4B_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_2$ and ${}^4B_1 \rightarrow {}^4E^b$, respectively.

Iron complexes :

The magnetic moment of iron complexes lie in the range 5.78–5.92 B.M., corresponding to five unpaired electrons, which is close to the predicted high spin values for these metal ions^{23,24}. The electronic spectra of the iron complexes show bands at 9230–9300 ($\epsilon = 3.77 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 14770–14910 ($\epsilon = 4.56 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 26325–26680 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 5.84 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which are consistent with the reported square pyramidal geometry for iron(III) complexes^{27,28}. Assuming C_{4v} symmetry for these complexes, the various bands can be assigned as : $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$.

EIMS mass spectra :

The electronic impact mass spectrum of the Fe complex showed a molecular ion $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{NO}_3](\text{NO}_3)_2]^+$ peak at m/z 662 amu and Cr^{III} chloride complex showed

molecular ion peak at m/z 580 amu. The calculated mass of Cr^{III} chloride complex was 579 amu. Therefore, the molecular ion peak may be corresponding to the $(M^+ + 1)$ peak. The observed data were in good agreement with the proposed molecular formula that is $[\text{M}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2)\text{X}]\text{X}_2$ and suggest the monomeric nature of the complexes. In addition to the molecular ion peaks, the spectra exhibit other peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the complexes.

Biological studies :

All the macrocyclic complexes were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity. Of the tested complexes, six complexes (**1**, **2**, **3**, **4**, **5**, **6**) possessed variable antibacterial activity against the Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) bacteria while only complex **1** displayed activity against Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). All the complexes exhibit activity against *Candida albicans* while two of them **4** and **5** showed activity against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Tables 1 and 2, Fig. 1).

Table 1. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of chemical compounds through agar well diffusion method

Compd.	Diameter of growth of inhibition zone (mm) ^a				
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1	14.3	15.6	14.6	–	13.6
2	12.6	14.3	13.6	–	12.6
3	13.6	12.3	–	–	12.6
4	13.6	15.6	–	14.3	15.6
5	12.6	12.6	–	15.6	22.3
6	13.3	14.3	–	–	18.6
Ciprofloxacin	26.6	24.0	25.0	Nt	Nt
Amphotericin-B	Nt	Nt	Nt	19.3	16.6

(–) No activity; ^aValues, including diameter of the well (8 mm), are means of three replicates, Nt – not tested.

Table 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) (in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of chemical compounds by using modified agar well diffusion method

Compd.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
1	512	256	256	Nt	128
2	64	128	128	Nt	64
3	256	512	Nt	Nt	128
4	256	128	Nt	128	256
5	128	512	Nt	64	16
6	256	128	Nt	Nt	32
Ciprofloxacin	6.25	6.25	6.25	Nt	Nt
Amphotericin-B	Nt	Nt	Nt	12.5	12.5

Nt – not tested.

Fig. 1. Bar graph representation of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of complexes.

In the series, the MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) of various tested complexes ranged between 64 µg/ml and 512 µg/ml against Gram-positive bacteria. Complex 1 was found to be best antibacterial and complex 5 was found to be best antifungal agents (Table 2).

Conclusions

Based on various studies like elemental analyses, conductance measurements and magnetic susceptibilities, infrared, electronic and mass spectral studies a five coordinated square pyramidal geometry may be proposed for all of these complexes. It has been suggested that chelation/coordination reduces the polarity of the metal ion mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with donor group within the whole chelate ring system²⁹. This process of chelation thus increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal atom, which in turn, favours its permeation through the lipid layer of the membrane thus causing the metal complex to cross the bacterial membrane more effectively thus increasing the activity of the complexes. Besides from this many other factors such as solubility, dipole moment, conductivity influenced by metal ion may be possible reasons for remarkable antibacterial activities of these complexes²⁹.

Acknowledgement

Ms. Parveen thanks CSIR, New Delhi for financial support in the form of Junior Research Fellowship (File No. 09/1050 (0001)/2012-EMR-1). Thanks are also due

to Microbiology Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra for providing carrying out antimicrobial activity.

References

1. D. P. Singh, M. Kamboj and K. Jain, *Inter. J. Chem. Research*, 2012, **3**, 21; L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, New York, 1989.
2. J. Hu, J. L. Barbour and W. G. Gokel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 9486; L. Cronin, J. S. Clark, S. Parsons, T. Nakamura and N. Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 1347; W. Lowe, S. Bratter and J. Buddrus, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2001, **38**, 305; G. Topal, N. Demirel, M. Togrul, Y. Turgut and H. Hogsoren, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2001, **38**, 281.
3. J. D. Silversides, C. C. Allan and S. J. Archibald, *Dalton Trans.*, 2007, **9**, 971.
4. M. B. Inoue, C. A. Villegas, K. Asano, M. Nakamura, M. Inoue and Q. Fernando, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 2480.
5. S. C. Menon, A. Panda, H. B. Singh and R. J. Butcher, *Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 143.
6. T. Clifford, A. M. Danby, P. D. Lightfoot, T. Richens and R. W. Hay, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 240.
7. M. Rosignoli, P. V. Bernhardt, G. A. Lawrence and M. Maaeder, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 323.
8. E. Fry, B. Graham, L. Spiccia, D. C. R. Hockles and E. R. T. Tiekink, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 827.
9. A. K. Sharma and S. Chandra, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2011, **78**, 337.
10. G. A. Melson, "Coordination Chemistry of Macrocy-

- lic Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1979; R. H. Dixon, "Reproductive Toxicology", Rawen Press, New York, 1985, p. 309.
11. M. A. Pujar, B. S. Hadimani, S. M. Gaddad and Y. F. Neelgund, *Current Science*, 1986, **55**, 353; S. Chandra and K. Gupta, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 196.
 12. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., Longman, London, 1989.
 13. K. R. Aneja, C. Sharma and R. Joshi, *Journal of Microbiology*, 2011, **4**, 175.
 14. R. Kumar and R. Singh, *Turk. J. Chem.* 2006, **30**, 77; W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
 15. D. P. Singh and R. Kumar, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **72**, 1069.
 16. D. P. Singh, R. Kumar and P. Tyagi, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2006, **31**, 970.
 17. Z. A. Siddqi, M. Khan, M. Khalid and S. Kumar, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 927.
 18. D. P. Singh, N. Shishodia, B. P. Yadav and V. B. Rana, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2229.
 19. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds, Part B", 5th ed., Wiley, New York, 1997.
 20. S. Chandra and R. Kumar, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 269.
 21. V. B. Rana, D. P. Singh, P. Singh and M. P. Singh, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1982, **7**, 174.
 22. J. R. Ferraro, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971.
 23. B. N. Figgis and J. Lewis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **6**, 37.
 24. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 22nd ed., East-West Press, New Delhi, 1993.
 25. J. S. Wood, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **16**, 227.
 26. D. P. Singh and V. B. Rana, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **14**, 2901.
 27. D. P. Singh, K. Kumar and C. Sharma, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 3299.
 28. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
 29. Z. H. Chohan, H. Pervez, A. Rauf, K. M. Khan and C. T. Supuran, *J. Enz. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **19**, 417.